

THE INFLUENCE OF VCA ON HEALTHCARE

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Abstract

Virtual customer assistants have recently become popular in a range of sectors and is now starting to become more relevant in the healthcare industry. Telehealth is the use of medical information which is exchanged through electronic communication (Tuckson et al, 2017) to better a patient's health. The use of telehealth has been increasing over the years but since the COVID-19 pandemic there has been a spike in adoption. This study looks at the influence of Virtual Customer Assistants on healthcare and if this is an addition or replacement to traditional healthcare. To find the answers to these questions, literature research was conducted to answer three research questions. The results showed that VCA's have a positive influence on the overall healthcare sector but that the technology is not mature enough to replace traditional healthcare. Further research should be conducted in regards to the use of VCA's and legislation when it comes to privacy of patients.

Keywords: *Healthcare, Industry, Virtual, Customer*

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Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic made the importance of good healthcare prevalent throughout the world. The COVID-19 pandemic did not only show the importance of healthcare but also changed the way people interact with the healthcare system. Lockdowns and social distancing resulted in the widespread adoption of telehealth (Anthony Jnr., B. (2021). According to Tuckson et al (2017) Telehealth is: "A term used interchangeably with telemedicine that has been defined as the use of medical information that is exchanged from one site to another through electronic communication to improve a patient's health." Recent studies show that before covid hit the USA only 1% of the users of the Metro Health systems in Cleveland Ohio used Telehealth but that this rose to 75% in the first two weeks of the pandemic (Bird, 2021). This of course is an extreme growth in a small time period and leads to the question if the most effective telehealth measures were used and what innovation affects current telehealth. This paper looks at the innovation of telehealth and how specifically Virtual Customer Assistants play a role in the healthcare system.

Relevance

The growth of the Telehealth market in combination with new technologies ask for research in the combined domain of Virtual customer assistants and traditional telehealth. Virtual Customer Assistants (VCA) and CPaaS (Communication Platforms as a Service) help patients 24/7 and can fulfil certain tasks that used to be done by humans (Vox, 2021). This is particularly important because of the shortages of healthcare workers. This research will also be important for managers to get a better understanding of Virtual Customer Assistants in combination with healthcare because there has not been a lot of research in this domain.

Problem Statement

In modern times everything is digitalized and every sector is trying to digitize their services (Calvino et al, 2019). Virtual Customer Assistants (VCA) is one of these modern developments (Druidai, 2021). VCA is providing classical healthcare via digital services, such as chatting, video calling and SMS APIs. Gartner describes VCA as "A virtual customer assistant is a business application that stimulates a conversation in order to deliver information and, if advanced, takes action on behalf of the customer to perform transactions" (Gartner). Different aspects come into play when looking at VCA in the healthcare industry, think of privacy and trust of a citizen in the medical expert (May & Denecke, 2021). In this research we will look into this development of VCA and if this trend is an addition or a replacement to the classical healthcare industry. When we look at VCA in practice combined with the healthcare industry, we need to make a distinction about the different applications. VCA can be divided into two different applications (Gavstech), IVA (Intelligent Virtual Assistant) and MVA (Medical Virtual Assistants). In this research both these different applications will be combined as terminology into VCA to give a comprehensive answer to the main research question.

The knowledge gap which will be addressed in this research, is the question if this trend (VCA) is an addition or a replacement to the classical healthcare industry. This knowledge gap will be addressed through different aspects and will be answered with existing literature.

Theoretical Framework

Based on the knowledge gap, the problem statement is formulated:

“What is the influence of Virtual Customer Assistants (VCA) on healthcare?”

To properly address this problem statement, more investigation is needed about the background of medical services and telehealth, the Virtual Customer Assistants (VCA), and the impact of the VCA on the business. This investigation is structured with research questions. The first two research questions have a theoretical background and are used to form a definition about healthcare and VCA, and to provide a historical background. The last research question is composed to research the relationship between VCA and healthcare.

- *What is the background of medical services and telehealth within healthcare?*
- *What is a Virtual Customer Assistant (VCA)?*
- *Is the VCA an addition or a replacement to the classical healthcare industry?*

Conceptual model

Figure 1, conceptual model

In this research ‘medical services within telehealth’ is the independent variable. Telehealth is defined as the use of telecommunications and information technologies to share information and provide medical services (Chin-Ching, Dievler, Robbins, & Sripipatana, 2018). The ‘healthcare performances’ is the dependent variable. IBM describes healthcare performances as overarching terminology for reducing costs, improving quality of care, and increasing efficiency of care delivery. The ‘Virtual Customer Assistant’ is believed to be a quasi-moderator that has a direct positive influence on healthcare performances. The VCA is a business application that simulates a conversation to deliver information (Gartner, Inc., 2021). This research does not focus on the relationship between the independent (medical services within telehealth) and the dependent variable (healthcare performances), but only on the possibly positive relation between the quasi moderator (Virtual Customer Assistant) and the dependent variable (healthcare performances). To conclude, this research focusses on the following hypothesis:

H1: Virtual Customer Assistants positively affect healthcare performances.

Methodology

To answer the research questions and finally the hypothesis, the method of literature research is used. Literature is defined as the body of knowledge available to you or what is already known and written down that is relevant to your research project. Multiple existing literature has been reviewed to form a conclusive answer. This existing literature is purely academic and all peer reviewed. Furthermore, all literature is relevant for this research. The next chapter results of the literature research can be found in the next chapter. The next chapter contains all the answers to the research questions and forms an answer whether the VCA is an addition or a replacement to the classical healthcare industry.

Results

To form a conclusive answer to the main research question “*What is the influence of Virtual Customer Assistants (VCA) on healthcare?*” The sub-research questions will be answered, starting with the first research question.

“What is the background of medical services and telehealth within healthcare”

The definition of telehealth can vary a lot based on the perspective one uses. Chin-Ching et al (2018) uses the following definition from the American Health Resources and Services Administration “The use of telecommunications and information technologies to share information and provide clinical care, education, public health, and administrative services at a distance.”.

Telehealth is not an unknown practice and has been common in certain aspects of healthcare for years to provide medical services. These medical services can consist of providing a consultation with a patient, remote patient monitoring or using devices to collect vital signs or blood glucose levels to supplement the use of visiting nurses (Romero, 2020). The term telehealth has evolved compared to its traditional use. Although medical care was initially the only justification for telehealth (hence the term telemedicine is also used), the scope has expanded to include supporting care-related processes, such as planning, coordination, and education (Bashshur, 2000).

Telehealth finds its support in the potential to increase efficiency and reach patients, blocked by access barriers. According to Gilman and Stensland (2013) there had been a long-standing hope to use telehealth to cover the lack of medical specialists in rural areas. Results from multiple studies have concluded that certain treatments provided through telehealth resulted in the same equivalent results as face-to-face treatments. Richardson et al examined literature to come to this conclusion (Richardson et al., 2009). Their results were based on the largest randomized and controlled telehealth trial (at the time) (O’Reilly et al., 2007). The Agency of Healthcare Research and Quality also came to the same conclusion, with telehealth being most effective on treatments which rely on verbal interactions (Hersh et al., 2006). The use of telehealth had been modest and in a growing phase. COVID-19 became a significant driver which significantly increased the adoption of telehealth, which became a necessity (Romero, 2020).

“What is a Virtual Customer Assistant (VCA)?”

To get a full understanding of the influence of VCA’s on telehealth we need to define what a virtual customer assistant is and how it can be used in telehealth. According to Gartner, Inc. (2021): “A virtual customer assistant (VCA) is a business application that simulates a conversation in order to deliver information and, if advanced, takes action on behalf of the customer to perform transactions.”

VCA’s can support Voice and text based engagement with a customer by using different mediums like: SMS, Mobile apps and other web based interfaces (Gartner, Inc., 2021). In the context of telehealth this means that VCA’s can answer questions of patients, remind them to take medicine and self-diagnose. Telehealth innovations increase access to health information, enhance patient-provider communication, and improve patient care (Maarup, M. 2021). VCA’s do not only change the care for patients but also the way that physicians do their work as VCA’s can work autonomously. A good example of a job that can be taken out of hand by an VCA is the interviewing of a patient by a nurse (Maarup, M. 2021).

A good example of a Healthcare VCA that is used in China is the doctor Bot. China is one of the leading countries in the world when it comes to the usage of VCA's.

The doctor bot uses AI to process the questions of a user by text or a voice note in a messaging app. The bot can self-diagnose the user and give instructions on how to use medicine (Fan. 2020). Chatbots like the doctor bot give patients easier access to healthcare at any time of the day.

It is very important that a VCA is designed properly. Patients are more skeptical of using AI driven technologies like chatbots and there will always be a group of people who would rather talk to a real doctor (Fan. 2020). That's why it's very important that a VCA can link a patient to a human. The VCA can for example do the first part of the interview which is very generic and afterwards a patient can talk to a human.

“Is the VCA an addition or a replacement to the classical healthcare industry?”

To answer this question we have to look at the classical healthcare industry at first and how this industry is organized. In the classical healthcare industry the patient-doctor relationship is critical and the impact of the quality of healthcare is heavily influenced by this concept (Chipidza et al, 2015). The four elements (trust, knowledge, regard and loyalty) which are built in person between patient and doctor are now replaced within a digital infrastructure. This comes with a lot of challenges and possibilities.

VCA is for this purpose an empowerment for building this relationship in the early stages. VCA empowers the customer and industry to more accessible information to their own preferences. Customers can have support from AI in early stages of their treatment to get more relevant information of how their own (customizable) healthcare process could work, and to which facilities and doctors it could get access to. The domain of Artificial Intelligence in classical healthcare is therefore a big potential for this industry (Davenport & Kalakota, 2019).

An important element of the implementation of VCA in the healthcare industry is the application of privacy & risk management. With the digitalization of the healthcare industry increasingly difficult challenges arise (Shachar et al, 2020). For this element we could say that VCA is not mature enough to be a well, standing-alone application within healthcare. Organizations which handle sensitive patient data need to be HIPAA (Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act), which is the standard for handling sensitive patient data. The HIPAA was originally formed in 2003 and has proven itself quite functional, particularly serving its primary purpose, making patients feel safe giving their physicians and other treating clinicians sensitive information while permitting reasonable information flows for treatment, operations, research, and public health purposes (Cohen & Mello, 2018). There is also criticism that the limited reach of the HIPAA will be an obstruction in the current development of the 21st century. This argument also shows that VCA is not a replacement (yet) for the classical healthcare industry.

With all giving facts we can conclude that VCA is not mature enough to be a replacement to the classical healthcare industry at this moment. The lack of domain knowledge and practical problems with data handling and privacy show that the potential of VCA is exciting, but for this moment and the next few years not sufficient enough to replace the classical healthcare industry.

Discussion

Despite the changes in healthcare, it is still not clear if the VCA is an addition or replacement to the classical healthcare industry. A comparison of our initial insights, findings and prior literature review provides some immediate insights. First, traditional telehealth has evolved. The practice used to encompass providing medical services and has expanded its scope to include supporting care related processes, such as planning, coordination, and education. COVID-19 has also been a driver for telehealth integration which significantly has increased its adoption due to the patient care limitations created by the pandemic. Second, we found that in the context of telehealth a VCA is a business application which answers questions of patients, reminds them to take medicine and helps with a self-diagnosis. Finally, Davenport & Kalakota (2019) argued that there is a lot of potential for the Artificial Intelligence domain in the classical Healthcare industry. The results might suggest that VCA has a significant influence on healthcare and might be on its way to replace the classical healthcare industry.

However, these results demonstrate VCA is still not mature enough to be a replacement for the classical healthcare industry at this moment. This is due to changes in payment (parity between telehealth and in clinical care, changes in privacy (patient privacy regulations) and changes in licensing (geographically) (Shachar et al, 2020). Although VCA is widely used in China, there will always be people who are still skeptical about putting their trust in a VCA instead of a real doctor (Fan, 2020). This raises the questions if VCA will ever be a full replacement to the classical healthcare industry. The generalizability of these results is limited by international legislation. There is no global standard regarding healthcare and privacy. Not every country is evenly technologically developed and not every citizen has access to the same technology.

Conclusion

Looking at the results and discussion the research question can be answered:

“What is the influence of Virtual Customer Assistants (VCA) on healthcare?”

The Virtual Customer Assistant (VCA) will have a positive influence on care because it strengthens the relationship with the patient. The VCA has a positive influence on each of the four elements of a relationship with the patient: trust, knowledge, regard, and loyalty. At first, because VCA is available 24/7, it can always support the patient when it is most needed. In addition, VCA enables the patient and the industry to obtain more accessible information according to their own preferences. In practice, this could support patients in early stages of their treatment to get more relevant information about how their care process might work and what facilities and doctors it might access (Davenport & Kalakota, 2019). The VCA can stimulate these conversations and provide information via digital services. It may also act on behalf of the customer to carry out transactions. This stimulates patient engagement because patients can participate more proactively in their own well-being and care. Better patients' engagement results in better health outcomes. In addition, VCA can fulfill certain tasks that were previously done by healthcare personnel. This is particularly important because of the shortage of healthcare personnel.

One caveat is the application of privacy & risk management. With the digitization of the healthcare sector, increasingly difficult challenges arise (Shachar et al, 2020). For this part, we could argue that VCA is not mature enough to be a good independent application within healthcare. Even though the VCA is not yet mature enough to be a replacement, it already has a significant positive influence on traditional healthcare. Mainly because of the empowerment of the patient relationship and involvement in care processes. In addition, the problem of the shortage of health workers is also addressed.

This research helps managers to gain a better understanding of the practical implications of the VCA in healthcare. This is a topic that has not been much researched yet. This research is a step towards filling this knowledge gap. However, as seen in the discussion, future studies should take into account legislation from different countries, the level of technological development and the willingness of citizens in different countries. This solves the need for a global standard in healthcare and privacy. In addition, this will also provide insight into the development and willingness of technologies in different countries.

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